

THE NECESSITY OF PRESERVING RELIGION

ضرورة حفظ الدين

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أبو الفردوس بينات باشا البجالي

مؤخرة. أستاذ قسم علوم القرآن والتفسير كلية العلوم الإسلامية الجامعة الإسلامية العالمية للدراسات الشرعية والإنسانية

***Corresponding Author:**abulfaradeesatnet@yahoo.com, abulfaradees11@gmail.com**Abstract**

This research came on an important topic, the importance of which was agreed upon by all nations, regardless of their sects, as guidance and as a reminder to the nation on its great impact on preserving these necessities, and on understanding their purposes from the Creator to attain happiness in this world and the hereafter, and I made it into the following issues:

– The importance of religion

– Pictures of preserving religion

In it I dealt with the definition of objectives in language and terminology and among contemporary scholars, then I turned to talk about the emergence and development of the science of objectives since the time of the Messenger, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, to the scholar Ibn Ashour and Allal Al-Fassi, passing through Imam Al-Juwayni, Al-Ghazali, Al-Shatibi and other imams of the objectives.

This research has been devoted to clarifying the first of the five necessities (preserving religion), which is one of the most important purposes of Sharia, and I have simplified it in detail.

And for this, I extrapolated the verses in which the conditions of earning are mentioned in the Holy Qur'an, using the inductive method, and then I interpreted the verses and explained hadiths, criticism and deduction using the analytical method.

Keywords: necessity, preservation, religion, pictures, importance.

ملخص البحث

جاء هذا البحث في موضوع مهم اتفقت على أهميته وشدة حاجته كل الأمم على اختلاف مللها ، إرشادا وتذكيرا للأمة على أثرها العظيم المترتب على حفظ هذه الضرورات ، وفهم مقاصدها من الخالق لنيل السعادة في الدنيا والآخرة ، وقد جعلته في المسائل التالية:

– أهمية الدين

– صور الحفاظ على الدين

تناولت فيه تعريف المقاصد في اللغة والاصطلاح وعند العلماء المعاصرين ، ثم اتجهت إلى الحديث عن نشأة علم المقاصد وتطوره منذ عهد الرسول صلى الله عليه وسلم إلى العلامة ابن عاشور وعلال الفاسي مروراً بالإمام الجويني والغزالي والشاطبي وغيرهم من أئمة المقاصد وقد خصصت هذا البحث لبيان أولى ضرورات الخمس (حفظ الدين) وهي من أهم مقاصد الشريعة، وقد بسطتها بشكل مفصل. ومن أجل هذا قمت قمت باستقراء الآيات التي ورد فيها أحوال الكسب في القرآن الكريم، مستخدماً المنهج الاستقرائي ، ثم قمت بتفسير الآيات وشرح الأحاديث والنقد والاستنباط مستخدماً المنهج التحليلي.

الكلمات المفتاحية: ضرورة، حفظ الدين، صور، أهمية.

on them to be taken from the rich and given back to the poor, so if they obey you, take it from them, and be mindful of their wealth, and fear the supplication of the oppressed, for there is no veil between it and God.”

And he used to command his commanders in jihad to call to Islam first, and to accept that from those who responded and refrain from it, as in the hadith of Buraydah □, he said: If the Messenger of God, So invite them to three qualities, then invite them to Islam, and if they respond to you, then accept from them and stop them). The religion of God Almighty, which is the most important of necessities, must be called to the people, and explained to them with evidence and proof; Because the call to it will increase the blackness of its people, strengthen them, and protect the religion from its enemies who lie in wait for it at all times.

Fourth: The obligation to rule by Islam

God has ordained the scholars of Islam in order to show people the truth from falsehood, but that is not only what is meant by preserving the religion. Rather, the religion must govern the behavior of human beings, and it must judge the one who has the right with his right. They attack their money and their souls. There is no principle on earth that is capable of preserving these necessities in order to guarantee them a happy life except this religion. Because it is from God, the Wise, the All-Aware of what is right for people.

The religion of God, which is the most important necessities of human life, can only be preserved by ruling by it and applying His law in reality. Therefore, God Almighty denied faith from those who did not judge by the religion that God Almighty revealed to His Messenger, may God bless him and grant him peace, and the Most High said: *وَأُولَئِكَ هُمُ الَّذِينَ يَرْتَابُونَ إِذْ يُؤْتَوْنَ الْهُدَىٰ وَرَأَى الْكُفْرَانَ كَذَبُوا لَكَ بِالْحَقِّ وَأَكْبَرُوا كِبْرًا رَبِّكَ أَكْبَرُ فَكُلَّمَا نَزَّلْنَا آيَةً لَّهُمْ تَبَوَّأُوا لَهَا إِلَهًا غَيْرَ اللَّهِ فَسَوْفَ يُعْلَمُونَ* attribute of immorality for the one who judges by other than what God revealed, and the Almighty said: *قُلْ إِنَّمَا حَرَّمَ ذُنُوبَ الْفُلُحِيِّ وَأَسْوَءَ مَا كَانُوا يَفْعَلُونَ*

The one who traces the lives of human beings will find the reality attesting that ruling by other than the religion that God Almighty revealed, corrupts that life, and makes it a life of hardship and hardship, and one of its necessities will not remain safe from aggression. God, and they were interested in explaining the functions of the guardian who is the first responsible for ruling in Islam, and they placed at the top of his duties the preservation of the religion, as al-Mawardi said, may God have mercy on him, when he mentioned - in the rulings of the Sultanate - that among the ten matters that oblige the caliph of the Muslims is “preserving the religion on its stable foundations, And what the predecessors of the ummah unanimously agreed upon.

and borders; So that the religion is guarded from faults, and the nation is forbidden from faults.” Imam Ahmad Shah Wali Allah al-Dahlawy, may God have mercy on him, said: Know that there must be a caliph in the Muslim community, interests can only be achieved with his presence, and they are very many, brought together by two types:

The first: What is related to the politics of the city, such as the disarmament of the soldiers that invade and subjugate them, the cessation of the oppressor from the oppressed, the determination of cases, and other things.

The second: what is related to the religion, and that the reference to the religion of Islam over all other religions is not conceivable unless there is a caliph among the Muslims who would most severely denounce those who left the religion and committed what it stipulated forbidding, or left what it stipulated on its assumption, and the Prophet ﷺ combined those needs. In four chapters: the chapter on grievances, the chapter on borders, the chapter on justice, and the chapter on jihad.

Fifth: The obligation to reject everything that contradicts Islam

The evidence for this is very numerous, and we will suffice to mention a few of them. Because this meaning is self-evident in Islam, God Almighty said: And in the hadith of Aisha, may God be pleased with her, she said: The Messenger of God, may God bless him and grant him peace, said: “Whoever introduces something into this matter of ours that is not from it will have it rejected.” Rejected, and in its sense indicates that every action is subject to his command, it is not rejected, and what is meant by his order here is his religion and his law, so the meaning, then: whoever his work is outside the law, that is, he is not bound by the law, then he is rejected, and his saying: (He is not on our command) is an indication that the work of all workers It should be under the provisions of the Shari’a, so that the provisions of Shari’a govern it by its command and its prohibition, so whoever is working under the provisions of the Shari’a is acceptable, and whoever is outside of that is rejected.” Religion, but rather to save all necessities.

Research Results:

After this easy tour with the maqasid theory, I can summarize the results of this research in the following points:

1. Islamic Sharia, with its comprehensiveness and lofty purposes, included all aspects of society's life, with the intention of organizing it in a precise organization based on achieving the interests of the people in the life and the future.
2. Islamic Sharia seeks to maintain the balance of society by applying the principle of enjoining good and forbidding evil.

3. It falls under the purpose of preserving debt, taking into account the jurisprudence of balancing between bringing benefits and warding off evil.

Finally:

This is my diligence, which I put before you, and I ask God to help us to serve His religion, and to provide us with His help, for He is the Guardian of that and the One who is able to do so.

Margins:

Al-Baqarah: 38-39.

Taha: 123-124.

The table: 3.

Al Imran: 19.

Al Imran: 85.

Al-Baqarah: 38-39.

Taha: 123.

table : 3

Al Imran: 19

Al Imran: 85

Sahih Al-Bukhari (1/37).

Muhammad: 19

He is Imam Shihab al-Din Abu al-Fadl Ibn Hajar al-Asqalani, the modernist of the Shafi'i school of thought. He was born in the month of Sha'ban / the year 773 AH in ancient Egypt, and he died at the end of Dhul-Hijjah 852 AH.\

He is the son of Al-Munir Al-Iskandari, Ahmed bin Muhammad bin Mansour bin Al-Qasim bin Mukhtar Al-Qadi Abu Al-Abbas Nasir Al-Din Al-Jazami, born - and died 683 AH.

Fath Al-Bari, previous, pg. 160.

Repentance: 122.

Ebn Taimia, Total Fatwas (7/314).

Al-Shatibi, Al-Muwafaqafaat (previous reference) (1/92,93), as well as (3/205 and beyond).

Asr: 1:3.

The Believers: 1:11.

Cow: 43.

Cow: 185.

The table: 38.

Light: 2.

Cow: 196.

Isra: 32.

Women: 36.

Joseph: 108.

Narrated by Al-Bukhari, Book of Faith, Volume 1 pg. 19, Volume 50.

Narrated by Muslim, Book of Faith, vol. 1, p. 37, p. 19.

Narrated by Al-Tirmidhi, chapters on the biography of the Prophet ﷺ, volume 3 - pg. 260, p. 1617.

Women: 65.

The table: 44.

The table: 50.

Imam al-Mawardi Abu al-Hasan Ali bin Muhammad bin Habib al-Basri (364, 450 AH), the greatest judge of the last Abbasid state, author of the classifications.

Al-Mawardi, Al-Ahkam Al-Sultaniyya, Investigated by Ahmed Gad, Dar Al-Hadith, Cairo, Edition 2006, pg. 40.

He is the great imam, Sheikh of Islam Wali Allah, Ahmed bin Abdul Halim Al-Dahlawy, known as Shah Wali Allah (1114-1176 AH), the imam of modernists in India, and a reformed Indian religious scholar.

Ahmad Shah, Hujjat Allah al-Balgha (2/735), see also pg. 772, investigated by Sayyid Sabiq, Dar Al-Jeel for Publishing, Printing and Distribution - Beirut.

Al Imran: 85.

Al Imran: 19.

Al-Bukhari - Kitab al-Solh - Part 3 - pg. 184 - h 2697.

Jami' al-Ulum and al-Hakam in the Explanation of Fifty Hadiths from Jami' al-Kalam pg. 52 Zain al-Din Abd al-Rahman ibn Ahmad ibn Rajab ibn al-Hasan al-Salami al-Baghdadi al-Dimashqi

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- [5].Al-Mawardi Sultanate Rulings, investigated by Ahmed Gad, Dar Al-Hadith, Cairo, Edition 2006, pg. 40.
- [6].Hujjat Allah al-Balaghah Ahmad Shah (2/735), see also pg. 772 invested by Sayed Sabiq, Dar Al-Jeel for Publishing, Printing and Distribution - Beirut.
- [7].The Collector of Science and Wisdom in the Explanation of Fifty Hadiths from Jami` al-Kalam Zain al-Din Abd al-Rahman ibn Ahmad ibn Rajab ibn al-Hasan al-Salami al-Baghdadi al-Dimashqi